

INTERIM TECHNICAL REVIEW REPORT 1 (PART B)

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Note:

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Forecasting and observing the open-to-coastal ocean
for Copernicus users

PROJECT	
Project number:	101133911
Project name:	Forecasting and observing the open-to-coastal ocean for Copernicus users
Project acronym:	FOCCUS

REPORTING PERIOD	
Please note that you must report on the entire reporting period.	
Duration:	from [01/01/2024] to [31/12/2024]

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1. INTRODUCTION

The Forecasting and Observing the Open-to-Coastal Ocean for Copernicus Users (FOCCUS) project commenced in January, 2024. In the first twelve months of the project, the first phase began with a focus on management tasks in WP1 such as establishing the project's shared data platform, regular meetings and coordination, and the Data Management Plan, as well as communication and dissemination activities in WP10 such as the project branding, logo, website, video, social media, and the Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan. Scientific work began in WPs 2, 4, 6, and 8, with observational and hydrological data improvements using novel techniques, along with planning integration into Member State Coastal Systems (MSCSs) and the design of coastal applications and integration into CMEMS. In total, the first twelve months of the project included the submission of eight Deliverables, the completion of eleven Milestones.

2. EXPLANATION OF THE WORK CARRIED OUT AND OVERVIEW OF THE PROGRESS

2.1 OBJECTIVES

The overall objective of FOCUS is to enhance the coastal extension of the Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service (CMEMS) to better serve coastal users and Member States (MS), by improving the use of Earth Observation (EO) data for coastal monitoring and forecasting, reinforcing coastal capabilities towards seamless delivery, and tailoring products and solutions to the needs of policy and society. These objectives have been selected to specifically innovate and evolve CMEMS coastal products where limitations have been identified, or where services have not yet been sufficiently matured. These include:

- those near coastal borders
- areas with high socioeconomic pressures.

In order to achieve this main objective, FOCCUS identifies the following five objectives, with their progress described more specifically per Work Package (WP) in the section hereafter.

Progress towards Objective 1: Improve pan-European innovative coastal observations in response to society and EU policy needs

FOCCUS has contributed to improved retrievals of required Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) in EU coastal regions, which are grouped considering the following 4 community sectors: climate, operational services, ocean health and ecosystems, and coastal change. Improved pan-European remote sensing (R/S, satellite and land-based) coastal observation retrievals are focusing on PHYS and BGC parameters, including sea level, sea surface temperature (SST), sea ice changes, seagrass and macroalgae, waves, shorelines, tides, and topo-bathymetry. This included maintaining a glider/ARGO float network and adapting an automated eddy-detection algorithm to SWOT based altimetry data, collecting and collated Fiducial Reference Measurements (FRM) measurements from an ISAR instrument ship deployment, and providing water reflectance spectra derived from automatic in-situ radiometric measurements.

New coastal products are being created by data fusion of in situ (INS) and R/S coastal data and by implementing new technologies and approaches for improving access, processing and data tracking. Specifically, data fusion for surface currents, harmful algae blooms (HABs), and Sentinel-2 MSI and Sentinel-3 OLCI OC products. In addition, artificial intelligence (AI) methods are being applied to improve the quality and to advance coastal observations. For example, this has been applied to beach-imaging AI-derived shorelines, satellite derived shorelines (SDS), beach-imaging derived beach wracks, and satellite-derived bathymetry.

An inventory of the current status of coastal data in different EU marine data services (i.e., CMEMS, EMODnet) is also currently underway to allow the identification of respective gaps, and discussions are underway with downstream WPs to plan how best to incorporate these enhanced data products and observations into coastal model validations and dedicated user applications.

Progress towards Objective 2: Improve land-coast-open ocean interfaces

FOCCUS has built on existing pan-European hydrological models E-HYPE, LISFLOOD and GREEN, and is developing a pan-European setup and calibration of nitrogen and phosphorus, particulate and dissolved organic and mineral matter transport modules to provide river discharge inputs for ocean models. New data affecting the nutrient flows were incorporated, and improved calibration routines resulted in a better description of internal model processes.

An Estuary Box Model (EBM3) is being further developed in order to represent the water exchange between riverine freshwater and marine salt water within three selected pilot estuary areas. Novel AI techniques such as adding the river mouth temperature as a new output field computed by a physical conservation equation and/or a ML algorithm has been incorporated, and an open face at the top surface of the EBM was also added, in order to optimize the estimation of EOVs. For training these EBMs, the current strategy leverages “learning datasets” built with SHYFEM MPI ZSAR code, which have been collected for the Ebro, Rhone and Danube river-sea continuum, and are in progress for the Po, Ofanto, Tiber deltas, and Portuguese rivers.

Land Ocean Interfaces (LOI) with inland-estuary modelling are in design to be established, for example assessing the link between LISFLOOD-GREEN and EBM to assess impacts and sensitivity testing on PHYS and BGC variables.

Progress towards Objective 3: Enhance and/or establish the connection of MSCSs to the existing CMEMS systems in order to improve the open ocean connection to these systems and enhance the quality and efficiency of CMEMS

FOCCUS will strengthen the capacity of CMEMS to support MSCSs by enhancing their coherency and by upgrading its systems for improved coupling and downscaling. Processing chains will be set up and tested to exploit new coastal ocean observations and new and improved algorithms, and this work has already begun. Information on the current use of CMEMS data for (BGC) modelling within the consortium has been collected and possible improvements to aid the use of CMEMS BGC parameters in MSCSs have been identified and discussed among WP6 members.

Connections of a selection of MSCS to the existing CMEMS systems will be set up through model nesting, and assessments of various nesting approaches are being conducted for each coastal system involved in the project, in addition to dedicated meetings having taken place to discuss this topic. An interfacing roadmap was created as part of Milestone MS6.1.

New modelling and data fusion approaches have been investigated to enhance the MSCS using stochastic simulations, ensemble approaches and AI technologies. For example, this included the implementation and pre-validation of new stochastic and multi-model ensemble capabilities in various coastal systems. AI methods being implemented include the use of AI downscaling through neural networks (GAN, SSRResNet) to enhance the resolution of target data, and the improvement of sediment field prediction and forecasting through the use of a ConvLSTM tool.

Progress towards Objective 4: Demonstrate the usefulness of the advancement of the observing and modelling systems through the design of co-produced applications in support of MS requirements

FOCCUS will implement efficient product chains to facilitate an advanced and seamless monitoring and forecasting of the ocean from the CMEMS global/regional systems to MSCSs through pilot demonstrations of new products and improved co-produced services between CMEMS and MSs. The applications are subdivided into areas (sectors/topics) and overarching use cases (policy, blue economy, human activities) and will demonstrate the added value for the protection of the coastal zone, the development of a sustainable blue economy (e.g., coastal and offshore operations), and the building of coastal zone resilience to climate change, anthropogenic pressures and natural hazards including storm surges, flooding, and degradation of ecosystems.

Because the applications are to be assessed and validated in co-production with MS stakeholders and partners, a workshop took place in June during the first year of the project with identified key stakeholders to begin the preparation for expectations towards the application building. This co-production assists with the general applicability of FOCCUS applications in the other MSCS and regional predictions and helps to enhance the impact of CMEMS and to promote the coastal forecasting and monitoring systems. Through a stakeholder survey, further needs and areas of improvement to the specific application use cases have been identified, and preparation is ongoing to collect data and refine

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coastal systems so that applications can be built in the next phase. An internal workshop on the specific definition of the coastal applications to be built in the next phase of the project has been planned.

Progress towards Objective 5: Maximising the uptake and impact through an effective campaign of communication, dissemination, exploitation and engagement activities and preparing the long-term exploitation of the project

To maximise FOCCUS impacts, communication, dissemination and engagement activities have started to be carried out for targeted audiences to raise awareness, foster dialogue, enable co-production and increase uptake and exploitation of project outcomes and results.

A public-facing website has been developed and published, accounts created and first posts made on social media. A project video has been created and is available on the project website, and a first newsletter has been sent. Several presentations were made in different key conferences already. Finally, a corporate design was developed for FOCCUS, including a logo and templates for presentations and documents.

To enhance the potential for exploitation of FOCCUS by MS and for uptake by CMEMS, the project’s R&I activities and pilot applications have been co-designed with MS partners.

An inventory is on-going to map existing MSCSs and their level of maturity, characteristics, applications and needs. The survey has been designed and will be closed in mid-February 2025.

The Copernicus National Marine Stakeholder Forum (Copernicus Marine Forum hereafter) is a key stakeholder group engaged in FOCCUS to link with MSs, to widen engagement and foster uptake by MSs. This is added value with low investment and yet high impact since the Copernicus Marine Forum already exists as a consultative group of MS representatives and experts created by MOi in 2022 to pursue efforts towards the evolution of services for policy and ocean governance, to foster deeper interactions with MS representatives and national entities in the marine domain, and to better integrate CMEMS with MS expectations and assets to better support MS and Copernicus-budget contributing states. FOCCUS was introduced and discussed during the two Copernicus Marine Forum meetings of 2024.

Exploitation will also be assessed through a dedicated Exploitation & Innovation Group (EIG) (Section 3.1.2) (1st meeting in June 2025).

To prepare for the long-term exploitation of the project, a strategic roadmap for the integration of FOCCUS in the Copernicus Marine Service will be developed.

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2.2 EXPLANATION OF THE WORK CARRIED OUT PER WP

The first year of the project was marked by the successful and timely completion of the following Deliverables and Milestones:

Deliverable	Due Date	Status	Link
D1.1 Data Management Plan	M6	Completed without delay	Link
D2.1 Data Reports	M12	Completed without delay	Link
D2.4 DWH use for 2024	M10	Completed without delay	Link
D2.5 DWH request for 2025	M10	Completed without delay	Link
D4.1 E-HYPE and Lisflood preliminary historical model data set	M6	Completed without delay	Link
D4.2 Technical report on E-HYPE and Lisflood	M6	Completed without delay	Link
D10.1 CDE Plan	M6	Completed without delay	Link

D10.2 Project video	M8	Completed without delay	Link
D10.3 Inventory of EU coastal operational systems	M12 → M18	In progress, approved for six month extension, see section 6.1 for details	

Milestone	Due Date	Status	Link (if applicable)
MS1.1 GDPR compliant project management portal created, including risk register	M3	Completed without delay	
MS1.2 FOCCUS data portal	M3	Completed without delay	
MS2.1 Description of data products	M12	Completed without delay	Part of D2.1
MS4.1 New hydrological components and EBM improvements designed	M10	Completed without delay	Link
MS4.2 Workshop on SoA Land-Coast coupling methods	M12	Completed without delay	Link to agenda
MS6.1 Interfaces roadmap	M6	Completed without delay	Link
MS10.1 Corporate design for the project	M3	Completed without delay	
MS10.2 Project website	M6	Completed without delay	Link
MS10.3 Social media	M6	Completed without delay	
MS10.4 Co-design workshop	M6	Completed without delay	Link to agenda
MS10.5 Meeting with Copernicus Marine Forum	M12	Completed without delay	

An overview of the aims, advances, constraints and near future plans of each WP can be found in the table below, with details per WP and task in the section following:

	AIMS	ADVANCES	CONSTRAINTS	NEAR FUTURE PLANS
WP1	<p>Ensure effective implementation of the project.</p> <p>Deliver high-quality work standards and innovation actions.</p> <p>Implement successful collaboration.</p> <p>Establish and maintain scientific excellence.</p>	<p>D1.1 Data Management Plan (DMP) submission.</p> <p>MS1.1 GDPR compliant project management portal created, including risk register completion.</p> <p>MS1.2 FOCCUS data portal creation.</p> <p>Day-to-day scientific and coordination tasks, including a</p>	<p>The project is progressing as planned, with all major objectives on track. No additional risks have been identified beyond the expected challenges of project execution. Activities continue according to the project timeline, ensuring smooth coordination and implementation.</p>	<p>Updates to the DMP.</p> <p>Further iterations of the technical review and final reports.</p> <p>Networking workshops and final conference.</p> <p>Continued management of the day-to-day scientific and coordination tasks.</p> <p>IT architecture further discussions and</p>

	Ensure the scientific objectives and impact of the project are achieved.	shared project drive, regular WP leader meetings, email lists, and regular communications.	The project has selected an appropriate data repository to ensure effective data management.	planning in collaboration with the first General Assembly.
WP2	<p>Improve the retrieval of required EOVs in coastal areas, to facilitate the data uptake in four sectors (i.e., climate, operational services, ocean health and ecosystems and coastal change), which will be linked with WP10/11.</p> <p>Design added-value products through data fusion.</p> <p>Boost the use of coastal observations for satellite Cal/Val purposes.</p> <p>Improve in situ coastal and river (WP4/5) data access, processing, tracking and traceability.</p> <p>Provide the first version of enhanced in situ and remote-sensing data to improve the ocean predictability through data assimilation and assessment (WP6/7) and for coastal services (WP8/9).</p>	<p>D2.1 Data Report submission.</p> <p>D2.3 DWH use for 2024 submission.</p> <p>D2. 4 DWH request for 2025 submission.</p> <p>MS2.1 Description of data products submission as part of D2.1.</p> <p>Improved the retrieval of required EOVs in coastal areas.</p> <p>Implemented novel data fusion techniques for variables such as surface currents.</p> <p>Incorporated use of coastal observations for satellite Cal/Val purposes.</p>	<p>The project is progressing as planned, with all major objectives on track. No additional risks have been identified beyond the expected challenges of project execution. Activities continue according to the project timeline, ensuring smooth coordination and implementation. Finding a suitable data repository-Zenodo was selected as the most suitable repository host.</p>	<p>Planned submission in February 2025 of the first datasets as Deliverable D2.2. This will provide the first version of enhanced in situ and remote-sensing data to improve the ocean predictability through data assimilation and assessment (WP6/7) and for coastal services (WP8/9)</p> <p>Mid term data status and statistics report.</p> <p>Continued efforts of WP in monthly meetings.</p> <p>Further integration of hydrological data from WP4.</p>
WP3	Not applicable.	Not applicable.	Not applicable.	Not applicable.
WP4	<p>Build on existing European hydrological and riverine transport model set-up E-HYPE (v4).</p> <p>Improve the representation of</p>	<p>D4.1 E-HYPE and Lisflood preliminary historical model data set submitted.</p> <p>D4.2 Technical report on E-HYPE and</p>	<p>Ongoing activities are progressing well, with no unexpected constraints. No additional risks have been identified beyond the expected</p>	<p>Work ongoing towards D4.3 Technical report on the design of estuary dynamics modelling approaches.</p> <p>Work ongoing towards D4.4 Technical report on LOC-interfaces</p>

	<p>river flows and associated riverine matter transports, specifically targeting European coastal basins.</p> <p>Extend the reference data set with European LISFLOOD results.</p> <p>Create a reference data set of modelled freshwater release to coasts for a multi-year historical period focusing on important estuaries across the Marine Service domain.</p> <p>Assess the current state of land-ocean interfaces and identify requirements for improved interfaces in a codesign process between hydrological, coastal, and ocean modellers.</p> <p>Design advancements in the numerical representation of the estuarine water exchange in order to refine the estimates of the freshwater release.</p> <p>Merge a 3D finite element modeling of the river-sea continuum with a 1D column-only box modeling of the estuarine areas for selected estuaries to get a cost-effective representation of the land-sea interface and properly force the member state coastal systems (MSCS) and relevant</p>	<p>Lisflood submitted.</p> <p>MS4.1 New hydrological components and EBM improvements designed, which improve the representation of river flows and matter transports, as well as estuarine water exchange processes.</p> <p>MS4.2 Workshop on SoA Land-Coast coupling methods completed.</p>	<p>challenges of project execution. Activities continue according to the project timeline, ensuring smooth coordination and implementation. Finding a suitable data repository- Open Science was selected as the most suitable initial repository host.</p>	<p>between hydrology, coastal, and ocean models.</p>
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	Copernicus Marine Services.			
WP5	Not applicable.	Not applicable.	Not applicable.	Not applicable.
WP6	<p>Enhance the quality and efficiency of CMEMS and MSCS by implementing production chains that better utilize CMEMS data in member state (MS) coastal systems.</p> <p>Set up processing chains that exploit new coastal ocean observations as well as new and improved algorithms at various points along these chains.</p>	<p>MS6.1 Interfaces roadmap compiled to collect expertise among WP members of interfacing with CMEMS and nesting techniques.</p> <p>Subtask working groups for all subtasks established, with regular meetings.</p>	<p>The project is progressing as planned, with all major objectives on track. No additional risks have been identified beyond the expected challenges of project execution. Activities continue according to the project timeline, ensuring smooth coordination and implementation.</p>	<p>D6.1 Implementation of CMEMS-MCSC interface and D6.2 Processing techniques work ongoing, with preparation documents already begun.</p> <p>Model nesting framework milestone MS6.2 Nested models implemented in a unified framework.</p> <p>New observation operators established with MS6.3 New observation operators.</p>
WP7	Not applicable.	Not applicable.	Not applicable.	Not applicable.
WP8	<p>Demonstrate the usefulness of the advancement of the observing and modelling systems through the co-design of applications in support to MS requirements.</p> <p>Set up applications to manage and protect the coastal zone, support sustainable blue economy, and build resilience of the coastal zone.</p>	<p>Potential users and stakeholders were identified for each application in each coastal system. On 13 May 2024, a technical workshop was organized in collaboration with WP10/11 to present WP8 coastal applications to the pre-identified advanced-level stakeholders.</p> <p>A questionnaire was distributed among stakeholders to gather feedback on the technical workshops and to propose further participation in the co-design of coastal applications, communicate requirements, and provide feedback, culminating with an internal restitution meeting.</p> <p>Coastal System Inventory created by</p>	<p>The project is progressing well, and activities continue mainly according to the project timeline, ensuring smooth coordination and implementation. Planning of MS8.1 Applications Design Workshop requested for a one month extension due to wish to capitalize on attendance at a Consortium meeting scheduled for February 2025-extension was granted, see details in section 6.1.</p>	<p>MS8.1 Applications Design Workshop results and report.</p> <p>Begin design of applications, in collaboration with stakeholders.</p>

		all partners involved.		
WP9	Not applicable.	Not applicable.	Not applicable.	Not applicable.
WP10	<p>Implement the communication, dissemination, exploitation and stakeholder engagement activities of FOCCUS.</p> <p>Design and prepare the implementation of a detailed Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) Plan, including communication activities.</p> <p>Engage key stakeholders from the onset of the project with the codesign of R&I activities, inventory of existing coastal systems operated for MS and involvement of the Copernicus Marine Forum.</p> <p>Define the conditions for exploitation of the project's elements with MS (including IPR).</p>	<p>D10.1 CDE Plan submitted.</p> <p>D10.2 Project Video created and submitted, posted on the project website.</p> <p>MS10.1 Corporate design for the project created and utilized at the year's various conferences, events, posters, and talks.</p> <p>MS10.2 Project website created.</p> <p>MS10.3 Social media accounts for the project created with an editorial posting plan in progress.</p> <p>MS10.4 Co-design workshop with stakeholders completed align with post-workshop questionnaire.</p> <p>MS10.5 Meeting with Copernicus Marine Forum completed.</p> <p>The project newsletter started in December 2024.</p>	<p>The project is progressing well, and activities continue mainly according to the project timeline, ensuring smooth coordination and implementation.</p> <p>The Inventory of EU coastal operational systems (D10.3) has been granted a six-month extension to better coordinate efforts with the DCC and improve the survey quality.</p>	<p>Results of D10.3 Inventory of EU coastal operational systems.</p> <p>Continued social media posting, newsletter emails, and project promotion.</p> <p>Continued engagement of the Copernicus Marine Forum.</p> <p>Develop plan for uptake in Copernicus Marine.</p>
WP11	Not applicable.	Not applicable.	Not applicable.	Not applicable.

Work Package Interconnections:

WP1 Management	WP4/5 Land-Ocean Continuum	WP8/9 Applications
Coordination and management tasks support all other WPs, providing structure for communications and scientific organization.	Use of hydrology and estuary datasets downstream in improving coastal systems in WP6/7 and applications in WP8/9, and use of novel observational data from WP2/3.	Models from WP6/7 form the backbone of coastal applications demonstrations.
WP2/3	WP6/7	WP10/11

Observations	Coastal Systems	Communications
Engagement with WP6/7 and WP8/9 to ensure that data products generated are designed to be effectively used downstream for coastal models and coastal applications.	Connections to WP2/3 for new observation products, WP4/5 for improved hydrology information, and WP8/9 as models form the backbone of coastal applications.	Receive inputs and support all WPs for communication, dissemination, exploitation and stakeholder engagement activities.

2.2.1 WORK PACKAGE 1: PROJECT MANAGEMENT AND COORDINATION

The overall objective of the Project Management and Coordination Work Package is to ensure the effective implementation of the project, deliver high-quality work standards and innovation actions, implement successful collaboration among the project partners and beyond, establish and maintain scientific excellence, and ensure the scientific objectives and impact of the project are achieved as planned. The major activities comprise:

- Day to day project management
- Scientific coordination, including quality assurance (KPI) and risk assessment (Critical Risks)
- Ensure efficient innovation management
- Clustering with EC, regional and international projects/program
- Data Management Plan
- Provide architecture design diagrams and guide the development of tools for data access

During the first twelve months of the project, there has been significant work towards the stated objectives of WP1. Day-to-day project management has been achieved by Hereon and with cooperation from all partners through the use of a shared Google Drive platform for document storage and coordination. In addition this was achieved through the scheduling of regular monthly meetings among WP leaders who comprise the Executive Committee, and with monthly meetings for each individual WP weekly meetings at the Project Management level, and regular dialogues at the Project Coordination level. Scientific coordination was carried out in a similar way, with the incorporation of additional platforms such as Open Science Framework and Zenodo for the hosting of data repositories and the creation of DOIs for document deliverables and datasets. The project’s scientific coordination was further initiated with the organization of the project’s Kickoff Meeting in Berlin, which took place in March, 2024 and brought together all project partners in person for the purposes of fostering institute communication and collaboration and planning the first phase of the project’s implementation.

Efficient innovation management was considered through the use of cross-WP communication and consideration of the upstream and downstream impacts. Regional and international projects and program links were also taken into consideration, and the FOCCUS project was endorsed this year by the UN Ocean Decades, under CoastPredict (Decade Action entitled “No 88.6. Forecasting Ocean to Coasts, Connecting Users”), ensuring the lifetime of the project and its impact continues beyond the scope of the project’s timeline. Efforts were also made to collaborate with the OceanPredict Coastal Ocean and Shelf Seas (COSS-TT) task team, which aims to help achieve a seamless framework for global ocean monitoring and forecasting. Collaboration with COSS-TT included the submission and acceptance of a joint abstract for the One Ocean Science Congress to be held in Nice, France in 2025, in addition to the joint organization of a COSS-TT event which will take place in June, 2025 in Brest, France and feature FOCCUS at the forefront. FOCCUS was also presented as an overview to the Copernicus Marine Forum at the 8th Copernicus Marine General Assembly, which took place on June 4 and 5, 2024 online.

The [Data Management Plan](#) was created with the assistance of +Atlantic and successfully submitted as Deliverable D1.1 in M6 of the project. This document takes into consideration a summary of the collected data which will be utilized within the project, including data types, formats and quality, as well as the use of data outside the project itself. There is emphasis given to make FOCCUS data products FAIR, along with consideration of the project data on project objectives and its impact outside the project, for example to policy and communications efforts. Data management and long-term preservation are discussed, in addition to data security standards and compliance with the GDPR. Finally, the [Data Management Plan](#) will be iterated in future versions, and improvements to this document were discussed after the initial submission, including updates to discussions on the metadata.

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The critical implementation risks described in the DoA remain relevant and have been effectively managed throughout the reporting period. No new risks have been identified beyond those originally outlined in the DoA. During regular FOCCUS project meetings, potential challenges are discussed, and mitigation measures are reviewed to ensure smooth implementation. The project team continues to monitor risks and adapt strategies as needed, with all risk management actions aligned with the initial plan. Further details are available in the Critical Risk tab in the Continuous Reporting section of the EU Portal. For each WP, further details on risk management and mitigation actions are provided in the respective sections of this report.

Regarding the deliverables and milestones of this WP, all of them are on track without delays. We are performing internal reviews of each deliverable at least two weeks in advance to ensure their quality. The following are already completed:

Deliverable/Milestone	Due Date	Status	Link
D1.1 Data Management Plan	M6	Completed without delay	Link
MS1.1 GDPR compliant project management portal created, including risk register	M3	Completed without delay	
MS1.2 FOCCUS data portal	M3	Completed without delay	

Connections to other WPs are broad, as the tasks in this WP apply to all others. The shared drive and repositories, [Data Management Plan](#), and scientific organization apply to all other WPs and provide them with the base organization and structure which they need to efficiently operate and communicate, allowing the scientific work to be carried out in the most optimal way.

TASK 1.1 TECHNICAL COORDINATION AND MANAGEMENT, REPORTING MANAGEMENT

SUBTASK 1.1.1 PROJECT DAY-TO-DAY MANAGEMENT

In this task, over the first twelve months of the project, HEREON has achieved the management, implementation, and maintenance of the Grant Agreement and of the Consortium Agreement. Overall legal, financial, and administrative management and reporting is ongoing successfully, including:

- Implementation and maintenance of a project-specific process for reporting and review based on FOCCUS document templates created by SSBE and internal reviews by WP leaders and all partners.
- Preparation for the first review from the EC.
- Management of day-to-day project correspondence through dedicated mailing lists and a shared project drive, in addition to monthly meetings of the Executive Committee (WP leaders), weekly meetings at the Project Management level, and regular discussions at the Project Coordination level.
- Creation and maintenance of internal collaborative tools for sharing documentation and communicating work status (e.g., the shared project Google Drive).
- Organization of the Kickoff Meeting in March 2024 and preparation for the first General Assembly (GA) meeting, which will take place along with the first Technical Review in March 2025.

SUBTASK 1.1.2 OVERALL SCIENTIFIC COORDINATION

In this task, over the first twelve months of the project, HEREON, CMCC, and MOI have enabled the implementation of quality assurance checks and risk management processes to ensure the quality of all reporting partners involved in each deliverable by:

- Ensuring that regular meetings of the WPs have been initiated by the respective WP leaders, with the purpose of checking the WP progress, plans, and achievements and to ensure well-coordinated and coherent communications across and within each WP.
- Ongoing monitoring of the project (including KPIs), including an internal review of deliverables two weeks in advance to ensure quality of the products.
- Establishment of the External Advisory Board (EAB), which was set in M2 of the project and will remain active for the duration of the project in order to provide feedback on project results and share information on related initiatives in which they are involved (such as COSS-TT). They are

informed about the project activities regularly through a newsletter and updates about project meetings.

TASK 1.2 COORDINATION WITH OTHER TASK 1.2 COORDINATION WITH OTHER RELEVANT PROGRAMS AND PROJECTS

Over the first twelve months of the project, HEREON, CMCC, and MOI have been actively coordinating with the SEC and partners' networks to establish strategic and technical links with other relevant EU and international programs and initiatives. The objective of this coordination is to align FOCCUS activities with ongoing efforts in ocean and coastal forecasting, ensuring interoperability, knowledge exchange, and technical integration across different frameworks.

The FOCCUS project has established strong coordination with key European and international initiatives, including the UN Ocean Decade, Copernicus Marine Services, and Horizon Europe programs. Over the first twelve months, HEREON, CMCC, and MOI have actively engaged with partners and stakeholders to ensure strategic alignment, technical collaboration, and long-term integration of FOCCUS within major research and policy frameworks.

FOCCUS has strengthened its visibility and impact through direct engagement in **leading European** and UN Ocean Decade programs. This coordination has also resulted in key leadership roles and advisory positions for FOCCUS team members, ensuring strong scientific governance and strategic input into related initiatives.

FOCCUS is linked with several EU and international initiatives, including:

- EU Mission: Restore our Ocean and Waters
- European Green Deal
- Horizon Europe project LandSeaLot (HORIZON-CL6-2023-GOVERNANCE-01-11)

In addition, the project is actively coordinating with the UN Ocean Decade programs and initiatives, enhancing its integration into international efforts on coastal and ocean prediction and fostering collaboration with key global partners.

- FOCCUS is an endorsed project under CoastPredict (Ocean Decade ID: 88.6) and is contributing to the coordination of coastal prediction activities. The project will be presented at the CoastPredict General Assembly in 2025, where technical contributions from FOCCUS will be discussed in dedicated breakout sessions.
- A connection has been established with the UN Decade Collaborative Centre (DCC) on Ocean Prediction at MOI, which provides a structured framework for integrating coastal forecasting systems. FOCCUS actively collaborates with the DCC Atlas to log use cases and coastal systems, supporting the harmonization of coastal data and models.
- FOCCUS contributes to the coordination of the CoastPredict InTime initiative, focused on integrating improved coastal and ocean prediction capabilities, aligning methodologies, and exchanging technical solutions across the international community.

The FOCCUS team is also engaging with European Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO) projects, reinforcing technical links between coastal and ocean prediction efforts:

- A collaboration with EDITO-Model Lab (HORIZON-MISS-2021-OCEAN-05-01) and EDITO-Infra (Grant ID: 101101473), where FOCCUS will contribute to co-designing future coastal forecasting systems in connection with Copernicus Marine Services.
- A joint session at the FOCCUS General Assembly in 2025 is planned, aimed at exploring interoperability between national coastal forecasting architectures and European DTO initiatives.

Through these efforts, FOCCUS has also contributed to coordination efforts within international ocean science programs. Project team members hold key roles in the governance and coordination of major initiatives, ensuring that FOCCUS remains well-integrated into related ongoing developments:

- Co-Chairing the DITTO program (UN Ocean Decade), supporting the integration of Digital Twins of the Ocean with coastal forecasting frameworks.
- Advisory Board membership in CoastPredict, contributing to the coordination of coastal forecasting and stakeholder engagement.
- Advisory trough participation in the Science Board of the DCC on Ocean Prediction, ensuring

- technical alignment between FOCCUS and broader ocean prediction activities.
- Co-Chairing the COSS-TT (Coastal and Shelf Seas Task Team), focusing on improving coastal modeling methodologies and their application to operational forecasting.

To further strengthen coordination across relevant programs, FOCCUS team members are leading the development of the first networking hybrid workshop, bringing together DCCs, CoastPredict partners, and related initiatives to enhance technical collaboration.

TASK 1.3 DATA MANAGEMENT ARCHITECTURE AND IT SOLUTIONS FOR THE PROJECT'S TASKS

SUBTASK 1.3.1 DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

Starting from the Horizon Europe (HE) Data Management Plan (DMP) template and community recommendations on data management, the FOCCUS DMP was designed together by HEREON and +ATLANTIC and discussed with partners for their approval and commitment on data management. The DMP was successfully submitted as [Deliverable D1.1](#) in M6 of the project, with plans in discussion for future iterations in M18 and beyond. In the context of WP2, SOCIB has also contributed to the definition of the metadata model for the coastal observing data products (D2.1, annex 1), including the update of standards vocabularies (BODC).

SUBTASK 1.3.2 ARCHITECTURE AND IT SOLUTIONS

In order to take advantage of collaborations with other efforts, MET.NO, SOCIB, MOI, and all other partners are planning a joint session with EDITO members to discuss architecture during the first GA in 2025. Further work on the C4 design diagrams will begin once the design workshops are completed as part of T1.2.

2.2.2 WORK PACKAGE 2: NEW INSIGHT OF HIGH-RESOLUTION COASTAL OBSERVATIONS

The overall objective of WP2 is to improve pan-European innovative coastal observations with novel methods in response to society and EU policy needs in the context of climate change (see Fig. 2.2.2.1). Specific objectives of WP2 which are being worked towards include:

- Improving the retrieval of required EOVs in coastal areas, to facilitate the data uptake in four sectors (i.e., climate, operational services, ocean health and ecosystems and coastal change), which will be linked with WP10/11.
- Designing added-value products through data fusion.
- Boosting the use of coastal observations for satellite Cal/Val purposes.
- Improving in situ coastal and river (WP4/5) data access, processing, tracking and traceability.
- Providing the first version of enhanced in situ and remote-sensing data to improve the ocean predictability through data assimilation and assessment (WP6/7) and for coastal services (WP8/9).

Fig. 2.2.2.1: Methodology for innovative high-resolution observing coastal data generation.

To ensure the completion of these specific objectives, the partners involved in WP2 have met regularly each month beginning in April 2024. Additionally, SOCIB, as overall coordinator of the WP, has participated in regular meetings with the other WP leaders to ensure effective cross-WP communication.

Regarding the deliverables and milestones for which this WP is responsible, all of them are on track without delays. The following have been achieved successfully during the first twelve months of the project:

Deliverable/Milestone	Due Date	Status	Link (if applicable)
D2.1 Data reports (lead: NERSC)	M12	Completed without delay	Link
D2.3 DWH use for 2024 (lead: SOCIB)	M10	Completed without delay	Link
D2.4 DWH request for 2025 (lead: SOCIB)	M10	Completed without delay	Link
MS2.1 Description of data products (lead: CLS)	M12	Completed without delay	Part of D2.1

Results from WP2 have been disseminated in different forums and conferences such as OceanPredict 2024 in November and the American Geophysical Union 2024 in December. Moreover, several abstracts focusing on WP2 have already been submitted to the following events:

- EGU 2025 (Vienna, April 2025)
- ESA Living Planet Symposium 2025 (Vienna, April 2025)
- One Ocean Science Congress (Nice, June 2025)
- European Coastal Videometry Workshop (San Sebastian, May 2025)
- Coastal Dynamics Conference (Aveiro, April 2025)

WP2/3 actively collaborates with and supports many of the other WPs. This is achieved through:

- Direct participation in WP leader meetings, fostering communication and ensuring alignment of activities. In collaboration with WP1, WP2 co-chair shares project management best practices, assists with forms and templates, and helps organize the FOCCUS General Assembly.
- WP2/3 actively engages with other WPs, especially with WP6/7 and WP8/9, to ensure that the data products generated in WP2/3 are properly designed to be effectively used in downstream WPs for coastal models and coastal applications.
- Participation in workshops and meetings related to WP8, including engaging with stakeholders to understand their needs.
- Contribution to the project's dissemination and communication activities, including participation in the project video, website review and communication and dissemination activities presenting the WP2/3 progress in the context of multiple conferences (WP10/11).

Risks have been managed in line with the DoA-identified risks:

- WP2/3 Task 2.2.1 Data fusion: the accuracy of the numerical ocean reanalysis used for deep learning could limit the skills of the final surface velocities reconstruction.
- WP2/3 Task 2.1.1 Risk assessment: dedicated FOCCUS products are derived from existing NRT DUACS products. In this sense, any delay in the DUACS processing delivery might impact our ability to acquire and process the observations. Although delays in the DUACS delivery schedules are rarely observed, this still remains a possibility.

TASK 2.1 IMPROVE PAN-EUROPEAN REMOTE-SENSING PHYSICAL AND BIOGEOCHEMICAL COASTAL OBSERVATION RETRIEVALS

SUBTASK 2.1.1 NOVEL REMOTE SENSING FOR CLIMATE

Sea level:

For this subtask, CLS is currently producing an experimental L3 S6A 5Hz reprocessing over the period 2023 to mid 2024. A first version of SWOT swaths L3 2km and 250m resolution datasets have been produced by CLS as well, and a new version is in preparation and will include improvements of quality flags, cross-calibration, and coastline accuracy (CNES fundings, but are potentially useful for coastal models and applications within the FOCCUS project). These improvements will benefit coastal (and polar) regions.

Figure 2.1.1.1 Aggregated SWOT swaths over 10 days (CNES fundings).

Additionally, comparison between SWOT swaths L3 2km and the L4 products based on Nadir-looking altimetry missions was performed by NERSC to assess sea-level anomaly fields emerging from the different altimetry concepts.

SST:

For this subtask, CNR developed the regional, daily, merged high-resolution (~1 km) multi-sensor (level-3S, L3S) SST product (from Sentinel-3, MetOp, SNPP, NOAA-20) over the North Adriatic regions (Mediterranean Sea) applying a new flag/masking scheme over coastal regions to display reliable pixels near the coastline.

For this subtask, DMI have produced bespoke satellite algorithms for SST in areas such as the Baltic Sea, as well as global products which can be used to assess coastal SSTs in addition to differences in uncertainty as a function of distance to the coast.

Sea ice changes:

For this subtask, The NERSC algorithm for sea ice drift retrieval from Sentinel-1 SAR data was adapted for processing data over Greenland and Svalbard and deriving land-fast-ice locations. Test scenes from January 2020 were processed and a test L2 product was generated and assessed. The quality of the test product was determined to be good, and the algorithm will be launched for full-scale processing.

SUBTASK 2.1.2 NOVEL REMOTE SENSING FOR WEATHER AND MARINE SERVICES

For this task, NERSC produced a dataset of ocean surface current radial velocity in the Norwegian coastal zone from the Sentinel-1A IW Doppler shift observations. The algorithm that was developed is based on a new calibration scheme, empirical GMF developed at NERSC, and ARCTIC 3km WAM wave model field (CMEMS). Additionally, a data assimilative model was prepared by MET.NO for the testing of radial velocities with suitable observation operators.

SUBTASK 2.1.3 NOVEL REMOTE SENSING FOR OCEAN HEALTH AND ECOSYSTEMS

BGC products and indicators:

For this subtask, CNR developed weekly Chlorophyll-a and Total Suspended Matter concentrations at the sea surface from S3-OLCI time series and related weekly anomalies and statistical trends, suitable for coastal applications and water quality monitoring at high spatial resolution (300m).

Seagrass and macroalgae mapping:

For emerged vegetation (e.g., during low tide), maps are based on spectral indices and temporal aggregation, and the product has been generated for summer during the annual peak of vegetation. For submerged vegetation, a new machine learning algorithm is being developed and applied in the Balearic Islands (Mediterranean Sea).

SUBTASK 2.1.4 NOVEL REMOTE SENSING FOR COASTAL CHANGE

In this subtask, SOCIB and MHD have advanced in the development of the following data products, which were included in [D2.1](#) and submitted in December 2024 and formatted according to FOCCUS data formats and metadata standards:

- High-resolution topo bathymetries
- Waves data product sheet
- Sea level data product sheet
- Shorelines data product sheet
- Tide gauge and topobathymetric data for the Western Black Sea

Moreover, a Seasonal Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA / SARIMA) model was used to harmonize long-term historical data from different open sources and establish a predictive temporal model for forecasting the sea level's monthly mean value.

TASK 2.2 INNOVATION IN COASTAL OBSERVATIONS DATA FUSION AND SATELLITE CAL/VAL

SUBTASK 2.2.1 IN SITU AND REMOTE SENSING DATA FUSION TO PREPARE NEW PRODUCTS DEVELOPMENT

Surface currents data fusion:

For this subtask, HF radars have been collected by CLS and are being used to analyse surface currents variability patterns and to validate deep learning solutions, and tools have been developed to do this. The learning phase of surface currents from Mediterranean CMEMS reanalysis (CMCC reanalysis MEDSEA) have begun, and it is based on a CNN algorithm (Convolutional Neural Network). Different input combinations are being tested to improve the solution. First results based on the test set (independent from the learning period) where produced data are compared with MEDSEA are very encouraging. The learning is done over the years 2005-2017, the test in 2019, (and validation in 2008 and 2015). A first test from real satellite observations is in preparation by CLS as well.

Figure 2.2.1.1 - Predicted hourly surface velocities (m/s) by CNN algorithm, over the western Mediterranean Sea and for 2019-02-02 at 0:30 am.

Additionally, SOCIB provided a HFR inventory for the Western Mediterranean from the European HFR network as well as drifted data, wind data from weather stations (inland and buoys) and surface currents measurements from moorings (available in each repository). Moreover, SOCIB has gap filled data from HFR from the Ibiza channel, well developed from the period 2023-2024, to be potentially used for validation of the data products.

Sentinel-1 Doppler shift ocean surface current dataset was produced, collocated, and compared with L4 geos.current (CMEMS), Mercator 1/12 model (CMEMS), and SWOT geos.currents by NERSC during the first twelve months of the project. An additional product for the Mediterranean sea was produced to be further compared with other sensors (HFR, SST, etc.).

Finally, the assimilative model is being prepared for new data by MET.NO, and evaluation of impacts is also being prepared through the definition of impact cost functions relevant to the modeling work in WP6/7 and the demonstration cases in WP8/9. Scripts will be made available in Zenodo.

HABS:

The HAB probabilistic models have been calibrated and tested by NERSC using as input the TOPAZ SSS and SSS and remote sensing PAR and SST. The product time series along the Norwegian coast is being implemented in NetCDF files to be made available in Zenodo.

Sentinel-2 MSI and Sentinel-3 OLCI OC products:

For this subtask, CNR developed bulk Inherent Optical Properties (IOPs), i.e., absorption (a ; m^{-1}), backscattering (bb ; m^{-1}), and water turbidity (FNU), at two inland site along the Po River (from S2-MSI) to be compared with IOPs off the river mouth from both S2-MSI and S3-OLCI, to assess bio-optical connectivity between riverine and marine waters.

SUBTASK 2.2.2 EMERGING IN SITU AND LAND-BASED PLATFORMS FOR INNOVATIVE SATELLITE CAL/VAL

Gliders/Argo floats:

An automated eddy-detection algorithm was adapted by NERSC to SWOT based altimetry data to assess the mesoscale field resolved by wide-swath altimetry. The eddy population was then collocated with Argo-profiling floats trapped by the eddies, to obtain a quasi-3D representation of the mesoscale features and assess the eddy-induced temperature and salinity anomalies.

SOCIB also contributed to maintaining the ARGO float network with an annual deployment of 3 floats in the Mediterranean Sea. SOCIB glider missions from the Canales endurance line are also available for the validation of the data products in the Western Mediterranean.

Additionally, MET.NO has new HFRs coming online, and will be ingesting in situ observations that include all data from our national partners as well as what is available through Copernicus. Specifically tailored provenance tracking in our DA system will aid the impact quantifications (WP6/7).

Fiducial Reference Measurements (FRM):

For this subtask, CNR provide water reflectance spectra derived from automatic in-situ radiometric measurements at Pontelagoscuro (Po River) WISP station in the 400-900 spectral range to validate spaceborne optical missions in riverine/deltaic environments.

DMI has collected and collated FRM measurements from an ISAR instrument deployed on ships of opportunity in the North Sea along three coastlines: Denmark, The Faroes, and Iceland. DMI also has the capacity to work with CNR and provide FRM instrumentation for upcoming voyages in the Mediterranean and Adriatic Seas.

TASK 2.3 NEW ALGORITHMS AND TECHNOLOGIES FOR OCEAN DATA PROCESSING, ACCESS, AND TRACKING

SUBTASK 2.3.1 IMPROVING QUALITY AND PROCESSING OF COASTAL OBSERVATIONS WITH ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

For this subtask, SOCIB has developed the following products defining the metadata models (more information about these products is available in [D2.1](#), submitted in December 2024):

- Beach-imaging AI-derived shorelines
- Satellite derived shorelines (SDS)
- Beach-imaging derived beach wracks
- Satellite-derived bathymetry

SUBTASK 2.3.2 IMPROVING TRACEABILITY AND TRACKING OF IN SITU COASTAL AND RIVER DATA

For this subtask, the status of in situ coastal data available in the Copernicus Marine Service has started (from a user point of view) considering coastal data as defined in CoastPredict. This is a multi-platform approach looking at the main Copernicus Marine EoVs (physics and biogeochemistry) which have been validated (QCed) by Ifremer.

2.2.3 WORK PACKAGE 3: VALIDATION AND IMPLEMENTATION OF HIGH-RESOLUTION OBSERVATIONS

This WP has a start date of month 14 and is thus not included in this interim review report as it has not yet begun at the time of submission of this report.

The overall objective of WP3 will be to assess the improvement of the pan-European innovative coastal observations designed in WP3. Specific objectives of WP3 will include:

- Assess the improvement of the retrieval of the EOVs in coastal areas, previously developed in WP2

- Validate and prepare the development of the added-value product, previously designed in WP2
- Boost the use of coastal observations for satellite Cal/Val purposes
- Validate improvements in in situ coastal and river (WP4-5) data access, processing, tracking and traceability
- Provide the final version of enhanced in situ and remote-sensing data to improve the ocean predictability through data assimilation and assessment (WP6-7) and for coastal services (WP8-9)
- Adapt the data products based on user needs and feedback to improve data uptake (link with WP10-11)

2.2.4 WORK PACKAGE 4: DESIGN OF IMPROVED MODEL INTERFACES IN THE LAND-OCEAN CONTINUUM

The overall objective of WP4 is to assess the current state of land-ocean model interfaces and to advance high quality freshwater inputs to better support coastal modelling efforts (see Fig. 2.2.4.1). The specific objectives of WP4 include:

- Building on the existing European hydrological and riverine transport model set-up E-HYPE (v4), improve the representation of river flows and associated riverine matter transports, specifically targeting European coastal basins
- Extend the reference data set with European LISFLOOD results
- Create a reference data set of modelled freshwater release to coasts for a multi-year historical period focusing on important estuaries across the Marine Service domain
- Assess the current state of land-ocean interfaces and identify requirements for improved interfaces in a codesign process between hydrological, coastal, and ocean modellers.
- Design advancements in the numerical representation of the estuarine water exchange in order to refine the estimates of the freshwater release
- merge a 3D finite element modeling of the river-sea continuum with a 1D column-only box modeling of the estuarine areas for selected estuaries to get a cost-effective representation of the land-sea interface and properly force the member state coastal systems (MSCS) and relevant Copernicus Marine Services

Figure 2.2.4.1 - WP4 workflow generalized components (2024).

During the period M01–M18 the ongoing work for WP4 went in two primary directions: continental hydrological modeling and estuary/coastal zones modeling. Continental large-scale models (E-HYPE and LISFLOOD+GREEN) are being improved and implemented to better estimate water and matter outflow from the European continent towards the river outlets. The SMHI’s E-HYPE is a hydrological and water quality model simulating nutrients and freshwater flow from source to seas at the same time. The JRC’s system uses two linked models: LISFLOOD, simulating freshwater flows, and GREEN, simulating nutrients. The JRC’s system uses higher spatial resolution (7km²) than E-HYPE (170km²). However, E-HYPE provides higher temporal resolution (daily vs annual computations with GREEN). The annual series can be disaggregated into daily by using daily discharge. However, the seasonal variability of concentrations cannot be properly reproduced with this disaggregation and more complex

methods would be needed.

New data affecting the nutrient flows were incorporated into E-HYPE, specifically information on municipal point sources. Improved calibration routines (Pareto front analysis, performance filters for parameter sets, assessment of outputs behavior) resulted in a better description of internal model processes, e.g. snow simulation or sedimentation and resuspension processes. The reference results from E-HYPE (daily river runoff, nitrogen, phosphorus and sediments to European coastal outlets) are provided by SMHI for the time period 2000-2019. The data of the GREEN model supported by LISFLOOD (daily discharge, annual total nitrogen and phosphorus loads and concentrations) simulation for the period 1990-2021 was provided by JRC. Both of these deliveries represent the benchmark data before any improvements were implemented.

In order to represent the water exchange between riverine freshwater and marine salt water within the estuary areas, an Estuary Box Model (EBM) is used here. It is an intermediate complexity column-only model, developed by CMCC and recently advanced by collaborating with CNR-STIMA, which solves the estuarine water exchange in terms of volume flux, salinity and temperature, averaged over the diurnal tidal cycle. Three pilot estuaries are selected within WP4 of the FOCCUS project: the Po, Ofanto and Danube estuaries/deltas. Additionally, the Ebro and Rhone deltas are to be proposed. The main advancements introduced so far within the FOCCUS project are: (i) adding the river mouth temperature as a new output field computed by a physical conservation equation and/or a ML algorithm; and (ii) adding an open face at the top surface of the EBM to properly represent the air-sea freshwater and heat fluxes as well as to properly introduce the biochemistry sink/source terms.

Further planned advancement within FOCCUS is to add a conservation equation for the biochemical tracers (jointly with University of Bologna) aiming at providing the net river release also in terms of time-evolving nutrient concentrations at the river mouths, besides the physics variables which are already solved. These upgrades aim at establishing a better connection between the hydrology and the marine circulation and biochemical models. For this purpose the link between LISFLOOD-GREEN and EBM will be tested.

A trained EBM allows a cost-effective representation of the net river release which can be easily coupled with the member state coastal systems (MCS) and relevant Copernicus Marine Services. The training phase is challenging due to the limited availability of observations at river mouths. The adopted strategy for the EBM training leverages on the “learning datasets”, built with SHYFEM MPI ZSAR code which allow a hyper resolution representation of the river-sea continuum test cases. The learning datasets have been collected for the Ebro, Rhone and Danube river-sea continuum, and are under refinement for the Po delta case and ongoing for the Ofanto and Tiber deltas.

In addition, observational and modeled data available for the Portuguese rivers will be shared with the consortium before being distributed widely. Similarly, temperature and salinity in-situ measurements of the Dutch Rhine-Meuse estuary will be shared. This data exchange among partners will contribute to building a comprehensive database to support ML-based clustering, ultimately aiding in the development of the EBM Tool into a fully relocatable and easily applicable solution for a wide range of estuaries.

This task will be supported with local knowledge from coastal experts participating in the FOCCUS consortium, expert working groups and from literature.

Regarding the deliverables and milestones of this WP, all of them are on track without delays. The following ones are already completed:

Deliverable/Milestone	Due Date	Status	Link (if applicable)
D4.1 E-HYPE and Lisflood preliminary historical model data set	M6	Completed without delay	Link
D4.2 Technical report on E-HYPE and Lisflood	M6	Completed without delay	Link
MS4.1 New hydrological components and EBM improvements designed	M8	Completed without delay	Link

MS4.2 Workshop on SoA Land-Coast coupling methods	M12	Completed without delay	Link to agenda
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Connections to other WPs include the use of hydrology and estuary datasets ([D4.1](#), submitted in June 2024) downstream in improving the coastal systems in WP6/7, and in the societal applications designed in WP8/9. This WP also takes advantage of the novel observational data generated in WP2/3, and contributes to the dissemination and communication as part of WP10/11 by participating in workshops and events, and contributing to the project's website, newsletter, and video ([D10.2](#), submitted in June 2024).

Risks have been addressed and managed in line with the DoA-identified risks, including:

- Organisational risks: team composition change and delay in the recruitment of the personnel. During 2024 a shift in the team took place. The new employee was hired and joined the team, two members changed their roles, however in general the team remains the same. The risk was addressed by timely hiring and comprehensively documenting the work progress.
- WP4 specific risk: failure to calibrate E-HYPE with added nutrient and sediment routines. E-HYPE is being improved constantly. In 2024 the first step of nutrient and sediment calibration was performed and the results delivered as well as an improvement plan for 2025.

TASK 4.1 DESIGN OF HYDROLOGICAL MODELS AND EBM IMPROVEMENTS

SUBTASK 4.1.1 DESIGN OF HYDROLOGICAL MODELS IMPROVEMENTS

For this subtask, SMHI improved the input data and process descriptions in the European-scale freshwater hydrological model E-HYPE4 to better estimate water, sediment, temperature, and nutrient runoff to the coastal areas. In addition, the JRC LISFLOOD model was developed with CMCC for simulating streamflow. The latest available Open-Source (OS) LISFLOOD model is version 4.3.1 (status June 2024). Benchmarks for both models were described in Deliverables [D4.1](#) and [D4.2](#). Improvement plans were described in [MS4.1](#).

SUBTASK 4.1.2 NITROGEN, PHOSPHORUS, AND SUSPENDED SEDIMENT ROUTINES

For this subtask, the SMHI E-HYPE4 model was recalibrated for nutrients (organic, inorganic and total nitrogen, suspended, particulate and total phosphorus) to reduce biases in the nutrient fluxes at the coastal areas. The sediment calibration was performed using an assessment of reservoir siltation. New data on nutrient sources and new calibration strategies were introduced to the model. In addition, the JRC GREEN model was calibrated with CMCC for total nitrogen and total phosphorus in seven European regions, to take into account regional variability. Benchmarks for both models were described in Deliverables [D4.1](#) and [D4.2](#). Improvement plans were described in [MS4.1](#).

Furthermore, a conservation equation for the biochemical tracers has been designed to be added to the EBM (working jointly with University of Bologna) aiming at providing the net river release also in terms of time-evolving nutrient concentrations.

SUBTASK 4.1.3 IMPROVED ESTUARY DYNAMICS MODELLING AND OBSERVING SYSTEMS UPGRADE

As a potential input to estuary models, continental hydrological modeling outflows to coastal areas were provided by SMHI to D4.1. For this subtask, a ML-based approach has been developed by CMCC for retrieving temperature and salinity at river mouth from high resolution EO satellite data in order to validate the modeling of the river sea continuum. The procedure for retrieving salinity is still in a development phase. The ML-based EBM code has been further advanced and implemented over most of the target estuarine areas.

TASK 4.2 LAND-OCEAN CONTINUUM - INTERFACES BETWEEN HYDROLOGY, COASTAL, AND OCEAN MODELS

Assessment of current state of Land-Ocean model interface, methodologies and approaches:

For this task, SHYFEM-MPI-ZSTAR code has been implemented by CMCC over most of the river-sea continuum, embedding the target estuarine areas by providing a new vertical discretization with respect

to the state of art for modeling river-sea continuum. This advancement is demonstrated to ameliorate the representation of the estuarine stratification and dynamics. Other ongoing work by CMCC includes:

- The temperature of river streamflow has been added to the inland open boundary and it is demonstrated to play a relevant role.
- Multi-year experiments forced by reanalyses have been carried out to build “learning datasets” which work as pseudo observations and support the EBM training phase by addressing the gaps in observational data.
- A Python3 Tool has been designed from scratch to estimate the “salt wedge intrusion length” from SHYFEM model findings in a more rigorous way.

In addition, for this task an on-demand model HBMOs has been set up in Randers Fjord-Kattegat by DMI with a resolution of up to 50m, and Deltares has gathered information on the in situ monitoring of the Rhine-Meuse estuary.

Hereon also pilots two coastal models: GCoast-GB, which resolves three major estuaries from the mouth to the weir, and GCoast-BS, which models the Danube delta system up to Reni, applying river discharge boundary conditions. Simulations show accurate representation of ETMs, fronts, and estuarine circulation with a cross-sectional resolution of 6-10 cells. The benchmark uses discharge data at the weir, and upcoming assessment studies are planned to compare these results against hydrological models from Task 4.1.

Inventorize and characterize main interfaces (estuaries) for the coastal-ocean downscaled models using WP2 remote sensing and in situ data:

For this task, Deltares has designed, developed and implemented a multi-level classification approach to define estuarine environments, based on a combination of MSCS output and CMEMS BGC data. This tool is currently being applied for the North Sea, and expansion to regions of the MSCSs of the other partners involved in this task has been initiated. Future plans include access of partners to in situ data of the Tagus Estuary with temperature and salinity collected by +Atlantic, access to in situ data of Randers Fjord sea level and river runoff by DMI, and access in situ data for the Black Sea basin by MHD. Interactions between task partners and WP2 have been initiated.

Design the interface of coastal models with products/tools from task 4.1 and assess with EMODnet near-real time data (WP2). Setting interfaces for study areas and performing a first intercomparison among the different methodologies:

For this task, a preliminary assessment of an explicit 3D Estuary-resolving approach was made for the Randers Fjord- Kattegat region by DMI. A preliminary assessment of a coupled approach between the advanced EBM and the Copernicus MFCs for the Mediterranean and Black Sea was also made by CMCC. Deltares assessed the current implementation of E-HYPE into the MSCS and designed the process with which comparison of the current and the improved E-HYPE version (4.1) with in-situ data will take place for the MSCS, with special attention to the Scheldt estuary.

In addition, within the MHD the HYCOM model is being used for dedicated services such as:

- Maritime navigation: Current and wave forecasts are essential for navigation safety.
- Search and Rescue Operations: Ocean current forecasts are used to optimize search and rescue operations at sea.

The evaluation of HYCOM performance in the Black Sea is being evaluated by MHD for the following:

- Current simulation accuracy
- Vertical stratification and mixing
- Temperature and salinity simulation
- River influence: Freshwater input from rivers (Danube) has a significant impact on the circulation and stratification of the Western Black Sea. The current work could analyze how this input is represented in HYCOM and how it influences the simulation results using data from WP2/WP3.

Workshop:

“The future of observing and modeling estuaries and river plumes” scoping hybrid workshop was planned by task members and held at CMCC premises on Nov 26-27th 2024, achieving [MS4.2](#).

2.2.5 WORK PACKAGE 5: BUILDING, VALIDATION, AND DEMONSTRATION OF IMPROVED MODEL INTERFACES IN THE LAND-OCEAN CONTINUUM

This WP has a start date of month 13 and is thus not included in this interim review report as it has only just begun at the time of submission of this report.

The overall objective of WP5 will be to assess and exploit the improvements of the hydrological models and land-ocean model interfaces (EBM and use of EMODnet near-real time data) in order to enable improved model-based monitoring and forecasting for the EU Copernicus Marine Service downscaled systems. Specific objectives of WP5 will include:

- Test improved hydrological model production and land-ocean interfaces in a preoperational setting consistent with TRL 5-6
- Implement advanced post-processing of modelled freshwater inputs in order to align them with available observations
- Compare Pan-European improved implementations of HYPE and LISFLOOD with regional hydrological models in selected regions to assess improvements in coastal interface in terms of river run-offs
- Test improved EBM and best practices of using river run-off EMODnet near-real time data to better connect hydrological models with ocean coastal models

2.2.6 WORK PACKAGE 6: IMPLEMENTATION OF NEW INTERFACES AND METHODOLOGIES IN COASTAL SYSTEMS

The overall objective of WP6 is to design and implement improved connections between the member state coastal systems (MSCS) and relevant Copernicus Marine Services. New methodologies in MSCS production chains will be tested, taking advantage of stochastic simulation, ensemble approaches, and Artificial Intelligence technology. Last, new ocean observation operators will be implemented in order to utilize WP2-3 outputs. Specific objectives include:

- Enhance the quality and efficiency of CMEMS and MSCS by implementing production chains that better utilize CMEMS data in member state (MS) coastal systems
- Set up processing chains that exploit new coastal ocean observations as well as new and improved algorithms at various points along these chains

Fig 2.2.6.1 (Left) Repartition of member state coastal systems, and (right) their connection with other FOCCUS activities (in red).

- Design and test modelling interfaces between CMEMS and MSCS (T6.1): Progress on the design and testing of modelling interfaces between CMEMS and MSCS involves the creation of roadmaps for improved interfacing (MS6.1) and the compilation of information on the use of CMEMS BGC parameters within the consortium. Members have submitted roadmaps which clarify the current design of MSCS and the interfacing with CMEMS, as well as the planned improvements. Task members have been executing these roadmaps.

- Implement new modelling techniques for use in operational production chains (**T6.2**): Progress on new modelling techniques involves setting up multi-model ensembles (i.e. aggregation of several (CMEMS and/or MSCS) products; DMI), model parameters perturbation approaches (CMCC, RBINS, SHOM) and stochastic modelling (SHOM) for uncertainty quantification in operational forecasting systems ; And training deep neural network for SSH and ocean currents downscaling (NERSC, HEREON), and for suspended sediments and chlorophyll-a plume forecasting (DELTARES).
- Identify and implement optimizations of integrated systems (**T6.3**): There is a clear link to WP2 in this task, which means that parts of the work here is to prepare data assimilative models for new observation sources (MET, SOCIB, CNR). As more files come online, there will be a testing phase using example output files from WP2 followed by tests with real data. There are also links to WP4 with regard to testing new input data for the freshwater sources (MET, +ATLANTIC). This work includes new or modified observation operators, dedicated setups for observation impact assessment, and methods for model diagnostics.

Regarding the deliverables and milestones of this WP, all of them are on track without delays. The following is already completed:

Deliverable/Milestone	Due Date	Status	Link (if applicable)
MS6.1 Interfaces roadmap	M6	Completed without delay	Link

For WP6, the main connections are to WP2 for the new observation products, WP4 for improved hydrology information, and WP8 as the models form the backbone of the coastal application demonstrations.

Risks have been addressed and managed in line with the DoA-identified risks, including:

- Diverging systems/different current level of interfacing with CMEMS:
The 19 member state coastal systems already have well-established data streams and production chains, and we have tightly coordinated the CMEMS interfacing action so as to insure planned deliveries.
- Dependence on dataset produced in other WPs:
Some developments rely on the inclusion of new data from observations (WP2/3) and hydrological models (WP4/5) in MSCS, but as for now, no delay was observed. If such would happen, the strategy is to divert the affected task efforts to another data type.
- Technical problems with MSCS are potential risks, but as for now, none that prevent the completion of planned tests have been identified.
- Changes in Personnel/key staff availability:
No specific issues have been reported on this side.

TASK 6.1 DESIGN AND TEST MODELLING INTERFACES BETWEEN CMEMS AND MSCS

SUBTASK 6.1.1 PARAMETER MAPPING

All members of this subtask have compiled information on the current use of CMEMS data for (BGC) modelling within the consortium and identified possible improvements to aid the use of CMEMS BGC parameters in MSCSs. The mapping of the parameters used to nest the MSCS within the Copernicus Marine Regional product has been finalized by CMCC as well.

SUBTASK 6.1.2 IMPLEMENTATION OF NEW NESTING CAPABILITIES

Progress in this subtask is ongoing and work is being done by all subtask partners. This includes:

- Deltares included the stabilizing effect of thermobaricity in the equation of state of MSCS. Collaboration occurred with the Deltares software developers to get this feature released into the publicly available software repository, to be finished in March. Deltares also trained and tested a deep learning (4DVarNet) model to gap-fill daily SPM images, to improve SPM forcing fields over the whole North West Shelf domain. By doing so, it is now possible to replace an old yearly average forcing with daily gap-filled data from recent satellite images. Improvements in the primary production model will be tested as well.

- Furthermore SHOM has had discussions with MOI about which data is best suited to force SHOM configurations, and implemented two new nesting capabilities:
 - A new, CROCO-based configuration of the English Channel - Bay of Biscay region, with upcoming stochastic capabilities
 - A calibration method applied to the Tolosa-SW operational model for forecasting surges on the Atlantic coast, including ongoing development on filtering low-frequency 3D dynamics from IBI.
- At RBINS, progress was made on the OPTOS V3 modeling system, which now uses hourly data from CMEMS NWSHELF_MULTIYEAR_PHY_004_009 products as a new open boundary for its high resolution hindcast OPTOS system. This was tested for years 2010-2019. Similar upgrades are being implemented in a pre-operational forecasting system.
- CMCC conducted an investigation of the impact of transitioning from daily forcing fields to the use of hourly frequency lateral boundary conditions for tracers and currents for this subtask. The assessment was conducted by comparing the results with data from available tide gauges within the domains.
- The assimilative Norwegian MSCS uses ARC MFC for boundary conditions, and an assessment of analysis increments at the boundaries is being done by MET.NO to support bias correction in the operational routines.
- DMI has implemented as part of this subtask a new nesting in DKSS, by using NWS MFC sea level and T/S as lateral boundary conditions. Calibration was made and a preliminary validation showed that sea level simulation in the Baltic Sea has been improved. In addition, T/S fields from BAL-MFC and NWS MFC were used to improve the DKSS initial fields.
- MHD utilizes exclusively in-situ data collected through its extensive network of tide gauges, current meters, gliders, and hydrographic surveys for boundary conditions. An investigation is in progress for this subtask on the use of AI/ML techniques (e.g., Explainable AI) to integrate in-situ data with the Copernicus Marine Service modelled data for improved nesting.

TASK 6.2 IMPLEMENT NEW MODELLING TECHNIQUES FOR USE IN OPERATIONAL PRODUCTION CHAINS

SUBTASK 6.2.1 ENSEMBLE APPROACHES

For this subtask:

- SHOM completed an implementation and pre-validation of new stochastic and ensemble modelling capabilities in the CROCO modelling platform.
- DMI completed an implementation and resing of multi-model ensemble modelling based on Copernicus MFCs and national forecasts.
- RBINS completed an implementation of new ensemble modelling capabilities based on the ECMWF ERA5 ensemble, in addition to an analysis of land discharges temporal properties to initiate subsequent ensemble modelling capabilities.
- CMCC completed the design and implementation of new ensemble modeling capabilities for the wave component of the FOCCUS MSCS, incorporating perturbations in model parameters to account for uncertainties in poorly constrained physical processes.

SUBTASK 6.2.2 AI METHODS

For this subtask:

- NERSC utilized downscaling of the DUACS SSH field by training a neural network of type Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) using SWOT-L2 as target data.
- Hereon tested the application of an ensemble convolutional neural network for spatial downscaling: ensemble super-resolution residual network (SRResNet), including spatial downscaling of significant wave height in a regional sea using ensemble SRResNet and linear regression.
- Deltares analysed outputs from a recently developed tool that predicts sediment fields from MSCS hydrodynamic data with ConvLSTM on a subsection of the MSCS domain. Additionally, they identified improvements in the convLSTM tool necessary for dedicated river plume

- simulations and initialized the steps to implement these improvements by May 2025.
- SMHI planned how to implement a ConvLSTM dispersion forecast tool and prepared high resolution (50m) MSCS hydrodynamic data of the Orust-Tjörn Fjord system on the Swedish west coast. Additionally, they started to prepare connectivity matrices to be used in the planned ConvLSTM tool based on the performed surface Lagrangian dispersion analysis with the MSCS data.

TASK 6.3 IDENTIFY AND IMPLEMENT OPTIMIZATIONS OF INTEGRATED SYSTEMS

SUBTASK 6.3.1 SYNERGISTIC USE OF MODELS AND OBSERVATIONS

For this subtask, MET Norway's 4D-Var system is being prepared for new observations, which includes impact assessments (cf. WP2 activities already described). CMCC worked on the development of a prototype system of the OceanVar data assimilation software coupled to the SHYFEM-MPI unstructured mesh model and successfully assimilated ARGO temperature and salinity in the southern Adriatic/northern Ionian area. Testing the ingestion of SLA data into the system has also begun.

SOCIB will use Ensemble Kalman Filter to assimilate data from various WP2 sources (HFRs, SWOT, gliders) into their WMOP model. High-resolution surface currents, land-fast ice, and HABs data from WP2 will be key inputs for MET Norway. For the validation efforts SOCIB will lead qualitative analysis, while MET Norway will focus on quantitative evaluation.

All partners collaborated in the beginning of preparations for D6.2, which will be due in June 2025.

SUBTASK 6.3.2 COASTAL-OPEN OCEAN COUPLING

For this subtask, MET Norway develops diagnostic tools for the model freshwater dynamics (indices based on integrated values, e.g. freshwater height etc.) and near surface drift velocities (rotary spectral analysis and use of Lagrangian drift model). Scripts will be uploaded to Zenodo.

2.2.7 WORK PACKAGE 7: COASTAL MODELLING SYSTEMS- VALIDATION AND DEMONSTRATION

This WP has a start date of month 13 and is thus not included in this interim review report as it has only just begun at the time of submission of this report.

The overall objective of WP7 will be to assess new methodologies implemented in WP6 and demonstrate their capabilities in an operational environment relevant to TRL5-6, implying short routes from research to operations if results are promising. In addition, added value of Member State Coastal Systems (MSCS) will be quantified, and impact assessments for new observations (WP2-3) will be made. Objectives will include:

- Test improved production chains and coastal modelling setups in a preoperational setting (TRL 5-6)
- Validate coastal systems to quantify added value to CMEMS products, with emphasis on metrics relevant to short term coastal ocean forecasts and use of MSCS for decision support
- Provide observation impact assessments from assimilative MSCS

2.2.8 WORK PACKAGE 8: DESIGN OF COASTAL APPLICATIONS

This WP overall objective is to design coastal applications able to demonstrate how to better address the selected ESCs compared to the state-of-the-art. Each application will consider the usage and show the value of observations (WP2) and models (WP4,6) improvements. Reference users' communities are: climate, weather and marine services, ocean health and ocean changes. Specific objectives include:

- Demonstrate the usefulness of the advancement of the observing and modelling systems through the co-design of applications in support to MS requirements
- Set up applications to manage and protect the coastal zone, support sustainable blue economy, and build resilience of the coastal zone

During the reporting period, WP8 activities included designing applications to address various environmental and societal challenges (ESCs) in several EU marine coastal systems (see Figure

2.2.8.1):

- **ESC1:** Applications aimed at better managing and protecting coastal areas, focusing on (i) pollution hazards in the North Sea/Dutch Continental Shelf (DELTA RES); and (ii) coastal erosion in the Mediterranean Sea (CMCC) and in Northwestern Black Sea (HEREON, MHD).
- **ESC2:** Enhancing the Blue Economy by supporting the multi-use of coastal and offshore operations in Mainland Norway (MET.NO), German coastal waters (HEREON), and the North Sea/Dutch Continental Shelf (DELTA RES).
- **ESC3:** Addressing natural and anthropogenic hazards and building resilience to climate change, focusing on (i) combating ecosystem degradation through restoration in the Mediterranean Sea (CMCC) and tracking marine heatwaves in the Mediterranean Sea (SOCIB); and (ii) monitoring natural hazards and extreme events in the Lisbon Metropolitan Area (+Atlantic), French Atlantic coasts (SHOM, MOI), and Baltic Danish coasts (DMI).

Figure 2.2.8.1 Environmental and societal challenges (ESCs) addressed by applications in WP8.

Potential users and stakeholders were identified for each application in each coastal system. On 13 May 2024, a technical workshop was organized in collaboration with WP10/11 to present WP8 coastal applications to the pre-identified advanced-level stakeholders. The workshop aimed to validate and refine the proposed scientific improvements in the FOCCUS project concerning Coastal Observation, Land-Ocean Coupling (hydrology), and Modelling Interfaces for coastal applications.

Following the co-design phase for each application, a questionnaire was distributed among stakeholders to gather feedback on the technical workshops and to propose further participation in the co-design of coastal applications, communicate requirements, and provide feedback to ensure the applications meet users' needs. Bilateral meetings were also held between application leaders and relevant stakeholders to collect additional requests, identify missing data and gaps in current services, key missing features of the applications, and potential provisioning of useful data and/or modeling inputs.

An internal restitution meeting was held on 5 July 2024 to discuss the feedback received from stakeholders. Additionally, the first monthly meetings between WP8 partners and application leaders were conducted to discuss updates on FOCCUS coastal applications, with details included below.

All WP8 partners contributed to define the Coastal Systems Inventory, identifying connections with the various WPs (observations, land-ocean, modeling and applications).

Risks have been addressed and managed in line with the DoA-identified risks, including:

- The dependencies from other WPs: WP8/9 lie at the end of the value chain: Delays in WP2-7 would further propagate into WP8/9. Failure to improve the components (observation WP2/3; integrated coastal systems WP4/5; models WP6/7) would risk meeting KPI -obj4. In order to address and mitigate these risks, WP leaders from WP2/3; WP4/5 and WP6/7 are invited to monthly WP8/9 meetings and dependencies and WP interlinks are included into discussions during the Consortium meeting,

Application Definition Workshop and General Assembly in February/March 2025.

- Potentially obtaining insufficient feedback from Member states and reference user communities during the co-design phase:
Following a technical online workshop, stakeholders were further engaged in bilateral meetings to ensure feedback and specific requirements were communicated to the application leaders. Many of the interactions provided comments and useful inputs from users due to already ongoing collaboration with the responsible partners. This also ensured that the collected requirements during the co-design phase were not diverging or overly demanding.

TASK 8.1 DESIGN OF APPLICATIONS TO BETTER MANAGE AND PROTECT THE COASTAL AREA

SUBTASK 8.1.1 POLLUTION HAZARD/RISK MAPPING

Deltares works on a coastal application for the Dutch Continental Shelf. Needs and areas of improvement have been identified with a stakeholder survey and through communication with the Member State Coastal System operators. They also made an inventory of existing model versions that can be used as the model base to improve upon.

RBINS works on implementing in the Lagrangian sediment transport model OSERIT-SEDIM the new met-ocean forcing (cf Task 6.1.2). In collaboration with FPS Economy (a stakeholder), gathering ship recording for all sand extraction activities occurred in 2019, along with preprocessing this information in order to estimate the amount of sand resuspended during sand extraction activities (both drag-head plume and overflow plume). Initial conditions are also being prepared for OSERIT-SEDIM.

SUBTASK 8.1.2 COASTAL EROSION DYNAMICS

CMCC has gathered requirements and potential improvements to a coastal erosion dynamics application through interactions with different levels of stakeholders (e.g., scientists and decision-makers) using stakeholder surveys. The design and implementation of the sediment core module within the coupled circulation-wave model system has been finalized, with a first application to the Tyrrhenian Sea (Mediterranean Sea).

Hereon has designed a framework to access coupled circulation and sediment dynamics using a regional/coastal model coupling the SCHISM hydrodynamic core model with wave and sediment modules (SCHISM-WWM-SED3D). Nested within the coastal model, a site-specific morphodynamic model (XBeach) predicts the erosion dynamics. The model system was implemented for the German Bight area with a local XBeach nest for the beach of Norderney Island. Storm events of different severity have been selected to assess the resulting erosion. In a next step, erosion mitigation strategies focusing on coastal vegetation have been evaluated, running the SCHISM and XBeach model configurations accounting for the vegetation effects and testing different layouts for seagrass, indicating high potential for erosion risk reduction. Another implementation of that framework was regionalized to access the sediment dynamics in the Northwestern Black Sea, successfully testing coupled SCHISM-WWM and SCHISM-SED3D configuration in that area, and currently progressing to the fully coupled SCHISM-WWM-SED3D system as well. These applications of the XBeach model are focused on beaches in Bulgaria, Romania, and the Ukrainian coast, and implemented in the pre-operational development phase. MHD worked on gathering data on sediment type along the western Black Sea shelf (from available reports, scientific literature, and own data) to be assimilated in the hydrodynamic model. Under development is a database for classification, distribution, and typology of littoral and marine sediments along the Western Black Sea, which will be incorporated with the model from Hereon.

TASK 8.2 DESIGN OF APPLICATIONS TO ENHANCE BLUE ECONOMY

Deltares identified the needs and areas of improvement to the blue economy application with a stakeholder survey and through communication with the Member State Coastal System operators. In close collaboration with other EU Horizon projects such as ULTFARMS and EDITO, an inventory of existing and work-in-progress model versions related to multi-use was made. From this inventory, the most suitable base model to improve upon was decided, and the required alterations and improvements were reviewed.

At MET.NO, freshwater dynamics and near surface drift are prioritised for the application with aquaculture. Lagrangian simulations based on coastal ocean models will be used to assess impacts on connectivity between locations.

Hereon worked on an implementation of offshore wind farm structures into the numerical mesh of their application. Parametrization, calibration and validation of physical parameterizations was undertaken to reproduce systemic interactions of wind-waves, hydrodynamics with offshore wind farm monopiles. Annual hind-cast simulations of coupled wind-waves-hydrodynamics including offshore wind farm structures were run, along with coupled runs of the physics-biogeochemistry including offshore wind farm structures. The implementation of a dynamic energy budget model representing blue mussel growth into the coupled physical-biogeochemical modelling framework was also completed.

TASK 8.3 DESIGN OF APPLICATION RELATED TO NATURAL AND ANTHROPOGENIC HAZARDS AND RESILIENCE TO CLIMATE CHANGE

SUBTASK 8.3.1 COMBATING DEGRADATION OF ECOSYSTEMS THROUGH RESTORATION AND THROUGH SUPPORT TO STRATEGIC EUROPEAN COASTAL AREAS (E.G. MPA OR KEY ENVIRONMENTAL ZONES)

CMCC gathered requirements and potential improvements to this application through interactions with different levels of stakeholders (e.g., scientists and decision-makers) using stakeholder surveys. Design of a NBS coastal application enhancing the model representation of the seagrass was worked on, with application to the Tyrrhenian Sea (Mediterranean Sea). Additionally, the idealization and initial implementation of the seasonal growth cycle of *Posidonia oceanica* in the coupled Circulation-Wave model system has been introduced.

SOCIB has contributed to disseminate a marine heatwave (MHW) application. They also participated in the following workshops and conferences regarding this topic:

- Mercator Expert Team Ocean Forecasting Workshop (03/2024)
- FOCCUS Coastal Applications Workshop (05/2024)
- Jornadas de Costas y Puertos (05/2024)
- 8th WMO Workshop (05/2024)
- Asociación Española de Teledetección Conference (06/2024).

SUBTASK 8.3.2 NATURAL HAZARDS AND EXTREME EVENTS (COASTAL FLOODING, STORM SURGE) WITH POSSIBLE SEA LEVEL RISE IMPACT

The application led by SHOM and MOI has been refined in response to the needs expressed by the MS, identified through the stakeholder survey. Future improvements to the operational forecasting system of extreme events for the French Atlantic coast are currently being developed.

The needs for coastal hazard protection was also identified by DMI through the stakeholder survey. The survey found that the main weakness in the Danish Marine Service is lack of wave impacts on sea level and wave run-ups on coastal erosion. The XBeach model has thus been implemented to integrate the impacts of storm surge and wave run-ups on coastal erosion.

2.2.9 WORK PACKAGE 9: BUILDING, VALIDATION AND DEMONSTRATION OF COASTAL APPLICATIONS

This WP has a start date of month 13 and is thus not included in this interim review report as it has only just begun at the time of submission of this report.

This WP overall objective will be to implement improvements, validate and demonstrate the applications designed in Phase 1 (WP8). A specific task will showcase the value of improvements and their benefit for MS and reference user communities (e.g., climate, weather and marine services, ocean health and ocean changes). Specific objectives will include:

- Build, validate and demonstrate the applications in support to MS requirements
- Assess the quality of Applications and gather feedback

2.2.10 WORK PACKAGE 10: COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION, EXPLOITATION PLANNING; CO-DESIGN AND STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT

The objective of WP10 is to implement the communication, dissemination, exploitation and stakeholder engagement activities of FOCCUS to maximize the impact of the project in WP11. This is being developed by (i) designing and preparing the implementation of a detailed Communication,

Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) Plan, including communication activities; (ii) engaging key stakeholders from the onset of the project with the codesign of R&I activities, inventory of existing coastal systems operated for MS and involvement of the Copernicus National Marine Stakeholder Forum; (iii) define the conditions for exploitation of the project elements with MS (including IPR).

Regarding the deliverables and milestones of this WP, all of them are on track without delays with the exception of D10.3, the inventory of EU coastal operational systems, which was approved for a six month extension (see details in section 6.1). The following ones are already completed:

Deliverable/Milestone	Due Date	Status	Link (if applicable)
D10.1 CDE Plan	M6	Completed without delay	Link
D10.2 Project Video	M8	Completed without delay	Link
D10.3 Inventory of EU coastal operational systems	M12 → M18	Approved for six month extension, see details in section 6.1	
MS10.1 Corporate design for the project	M3	Completed without delay	
MS10.2 Project website	M6	Completed without delay	Link
MS10.3 Social media	M6	Completed without delay	
MS10.4 Co-design workshop	M6	Completed without delay	Link to agenda
MS10.5 Meeting with Copernicus Marine Forum	M12	Completed without delay	

To achieve its objectives, WP10 has been connected to all other WPs of FOCCUS. Connections include receiving inputs from other WPs for communication and dissemination purposes, providing support to all other WPs for their communication, dissemination, exploitation and stakeholder engagement activities. WP10 provided support for the organization of the WP8-9 co-design workshop and surveys.

Risks have been addressed and managed in line with the DoA-identified risks, including:

- Risk: Diverging or overly demanding needs collected in co-design thematic workshops.
Addressing the risk: MOi assisted all co-design workshops and worked to translate user needs into achievable specifications for the technical WPs.
- Risk: Lack of participation in workshops.
Addressing the risk: workshops were organized online to maximize attendance. Following online workshops, flexible one-to-one interviews of stakeholders were held to maximize engagement and get direct feedback.
- Risk: lack of wider stakeholder awareness about the project and/or failure of the planned communication and dissemination activities.
Addressing the risk: a clear, step-wise and multi-channelled communication and dissemination plan delivering fit-for-use public tools to engage the key stakeholder groups of the project was set up. The status of stakeholder engagement is assessed to fine tune and optimise further stakeholder onboarding and engagement.
- Risk: partners leave, long-term illness of key staff, change of roles or poor partner performance and conflicts.
Addressing the risk: in WP10, there has been a change of position of key personnel. Re-organization of personnel was done in related institutes, with replacement of personnel. No conflicts were experienced.
- Risk: project personnel leave, team composition change, ineffective teamwork.

Addressing the risk: in WP10 one project personnel left for a new position. To this, it followed an internal reorganization of responsibilities and tasks in the corresponding institute to support the project and minimise delays.

TASK 10.1 COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION, AND MANAGEMENT OF PROJECT RESULTS EXPLOITATION

SSBE has led Task 10.1 by delivering a project communication strategy and a [Communication and Dissemination Plan \(D10.1\)](#). SSBE has also designed a visual identity of the project (logo, templates in D10.2). A website has been put in place by SSBE (MS 10.2, <https://foccus-project.eu/>, Figure 2.2.10.1) and a [promotional video](#) (D10.2, Figure 2.2.10.2) including interviews with FOCCUS partners has been developed and published, as well as a project brochure, validated by MOi as WP leader (Figure 2.2.10.3). The first FOCCUS Newsletter was prepared by SSBE and launched in December 2024. Additionally, SSBE is responsible for managing the project's social media presence, disseminating news, and fostering a vibrant community around the FOCCUS project. Partners have also published news on their website and / or relayed communication material (e.g., news on [HEREON's website](#), news on [MOi's website](#) and on the [Copernicus Marine website](#) done by MOi, news on [SHOM's website](#), news on [EUROGOOS's website](#), news on [CMCC's website](#), [ISMAR's website](#), news on [SSBE's website](#)).

Figure 2.2.10.1 - Visuals of the FOCCUS website.

Figure 2.2.10.2 - Screenshot of the promotional video for the FOCCUS project, hosted on Youtube.

Figure 2.2.10.3 - Screenshot of the FOCCUS brochure.

All project partners have participated in [D10.1](#) CDE Plan and [D10.2](#) Project Video, and have provided feedback and content for the FOCCUS newsletter, as well as the website which was launched in M6.

FOCCUS has begun its dissemination efforts through presentations at conferences and workshops and abstracts. These engagements focus on showcasing the project's co-production approach and technical developments in coastal data products, fostering dialogue with the scientific community and potential collaborators. Conferences where FOCCUS has been or will be presented (with abstracts submitted) include:

- 2 poster presentations at the AGU General Assembly, Washington DC, December 2024,
- 3 presentations (1 keynote, 1 oral, 1 poster) at the OceanPredict Symposium 2024, Paris, October 2024,
- 1 oral presentation at Jornadas de Costas y Puertos, Spain, May 2024,
- 1 oral presentation at the Asociación Española de Teledetección, Spain, June 2024,
- 1 oral presentation at the Mallorca Science School (MASS) 2024: "Interdisciplinary Science for Marine and Coastal Conservation in a Changing World", s October 20 to 26, 2024, in Mallorca, Spain.
- 1 oral presentation at [Marine User Days](#), in Lisbon, Portugal, 6 November 2024,
- 1 oral presentation at Oslo Symposium, on the theoretical foundation of operational oceanography and its applications, The Norwegian Academy of Science and Letters, Oslo November 13, 2024,
- 1 oral presentation during the 8th Copernicus Marine General Assembly, May 2024.

and in workshops, including:

- 1 oral presentation at EMODnet Marine Data for Ports, Marinas and Boating, October 2024,
- 8th IWMO workshop, May 2024,
- 2 Oral presentations at the International Workshop on Modeling the Ocean IWMO, 14th IWMO-2024 June 17-20, Sapporo, Japan
- Mercator Expert Team Ocean Forecasting Workshop, March 2024,
- 1 oral presentation at the 14th Meeting of the IHO-EU Network WG – 14ème réunion du GT du réseau OHI-UE, 29 May 2024 (<https://iho.int/en/ienwg14-2024>)
- 1 oral presentation at the DMI-BOOS Collaboration Meeting, March 2024;

and acknowledged in publications, including:

- Mihailov, M.E.; Chiroasca, A.V.; Chiroasca, G. Fusion of In-Situ and Modelled Marine Data for Enhanced Coastal Dynamics Prediction Along the Western Black Sea Coast. *J. Mar. Sci. Eng.* 2025, 13, 199. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jmse13020199>
- Hernandez, F., Garcia Sotillo, M., and Melet, A.: A description of Model Intercomparison Processes and Techniques for Ocean Forecasting, *State Planet Discuss.* [preprint], <https://doi.org/10.5194/sp-2024-39>, in review, 2024.
- Staneva, J., Melet, A., Veitch, J., and Matte, P.: Solving Coastal Dynamics: Introduction to High Resolution Ocean Forecasting Services, *State Planet Discuss.* [preprint], <https://doi.org/10.5194/sp-2024-44>, in review, 2024.
- Zlateva, I., Ricker, M., Slabakova, V., Slavova, K., Doncheva, V., Staneva, J., Stanev, E., Popov, I., Gramcianinov, C., & Raykov, V. (2024). Analysis of terrestrial and riverine sources of plastic litter contributing to plastic pollution in the Western Black Sea using a lagrangian particle tracking model. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 209, 117108. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.MARPOLBUL.2024.117108>
- Dammak, N., Chen, W., & Staneva, J. (2025): Toward an AI-enhanced hydro-morphodynamic model for nature-based solutions in coastal erosion mitigation. *Applied Ocean Research*, Vol 154, 104326, doi:10.1016/j.apor.2024.104326
- Pein, J., Staneva, J., Biederbick, J., & Schrum, C. (2025): Model-based assessment of sustainable adaptation options for an industrialised meso-tidal estuary. *Ocean Modelling*, Vol 194, 102467, doi:10.1016/j.ocemod.2024.102467
- Stanev, E. V., Gramcianinov, C. B., Staneva, J., & Slabakova, V. (2024). Thermohaline intrusions as seen by Argo floats: The case of the Black Sea. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 129, e2024JC021762. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2024JC021762>
- Nguyen, T. T., Staneva, J., Grayek, S., Bonaduce, A., Hagemann, S., Pham, N. T., Kumar, R., & Rakovec, O. (2024). Impacts of extreme river discharge on coastal dynamics and environment: Insights from high-resolution modeling in the German Bight. *Regional Studies in Marine Science*, 73, 103476. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.RSMA.2024.103476>.

FOCCUS abstracts were submitted to present FOCCUS at the EGU General Assembly (Vienna, AT, April 2025), at the UN Ocean Conference One Ocean Science Congress (Nice, FR, June 2025) and at the ESA Living Planet Symposium (Vienna, AT, June 2025).

To prepare for the exploitation of FOCCUS through the Copernicus Marine Service, the Project Coordinator was invited to present FOCCUS as an oral presentation at the [8th Copernicus Marine General Assembly](#) in June 2024.

TASK 10.2 MEMBER STATES - COPERNICUS ENGAGEMENT

SUBTASK 10.2.1 INVENTORY OF MS COASTAL SYSTEMS

EUROGOOS through RBINS designed and coordinated the production and diffusion of a survey to collect Coastal Forecasting operator's requirements towards CMEMS regional system data provision. MOI contributed to this subtask by advising and technically operating the construction and monitoring of the survey, and will collect the results and prepare the analysis. SSBE is helping to disseminate the MS coastal forecasting inventory survey through the FOCCUS communication channels.

The survey leverages existing surveys (Copernicus Marine Forum, Copernicus Marine MFCs, EUROGOOS) and the UN Ocean Decade: Decade Collaborative Centre (DCC) for Ocean Prediction (OP). Yet, a new and more dedicated survey has been designed within FOCCUS to address in more detail the interfaces between coastal systems and Copernicus Marine systems. An extension of the delivery date of the inventory of MS coastal systems (D10.3) to June 2025 has been requested and

The overall objective of WP11 will be to maximize the impact of the project through an effective campaign of communication, dissemination, exploitation and engagement activities to targeted audiences. This will be achieved by a full implementation of activities outlined in the CDE Plan (D10.1) and through the definition of the long-term exploitation of the project through a transfer toward the Copernicus Marine Service. Specific objectives of WP11 will be to:

- Build upon WP10 to further promote the project itself and its results to targeted audiences and other relevant stakeholders
- Maximize the visibility and shared benefits of the project
- Maximize the integration of the project outcomes, products and services in Copernicus Marine
- Maximize the project uptake, exploitation and impact by and for stakeholders

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2.3 IMPACT

In coherence with the DoA, the FOCCUS project is acting towards:

- Advanced European capacity for the efficient management of coastal areas.
- Links with EU directives that will improve the current assessment of compliance or not with the existing environmental or water related directives.
- Increased public awareness with regard to the importance of monitoring and preserving the coastal zone for a sustainable use of the ocean.
- Increased understanding of coastal zone dynamics, impacts of their use; building resilience of coastal zones with regard to a changing climate and increased human activities.
- Improved monitoring, forecasting and management of marine coastal zones for a range of applications and policies.
- Wider use of FOCCUS legacy products and developments by users of CMEMS and Copernicus Thematic Hubs (CTH) on coastal zones, supporting other applications and blue markets than those developed in FOCCUS.
- Expanding the number of CMEMS users and improving the support to those users, MS, and policy needs regarding coastal zones, whilst continuing to sustain the development of the blue economy.

Figure 2.3.1 FOCCUS planned impacts.

Focusing on innovation, the FOCCUS project started at TRL 3-4 level, and reached TRL 5 level during the first 12 months of the project for some components, and is expected to reach TRL 5-6 level at the end of the project. Indeed,

At project's start:

- **TRL 3-4:** In-line with the call ambition, FOCCUS will deliver activities achieving a TRL of 5-6, namely coastal product prototypes that illustrate the added value of different applications in the framework of demonstrations. At the project's start, these were in proof of concept or

experimental phases.

Current status:

- **TRL 4, working towards TRL 5:** Improved coastal observations are being validated in strategic coastal areas, and hydrological models are being improved with stage one completed of a two stage data release with metadata package for use in coastal model systems. FOCCUS is also building, in synergy with the UN Decade Collaborative Center for Ocean Prediction (DCC OP), an inventory of existing coastal ocean operational systems and working towards collecting and addressing their needs and requirements to enhance their interfacing with the Copernicus Marine global and regional operational ocean systems. Implementation of such interfaces and methodologies is being developed with a selection of Member States Coastal Systems (WP6), and the coastal applications are being co-designed (WP8) to demonstrate the usefulness of FOCCUS developments to better support Member States.

Expected by project's end:

- **TRL 5:** Improved coastal observations validated in strategic coastal areas, improved hydrological models, and quantifiable improvements in production chains and performance in coastal ocean forecasting systems downstream of Copernicus Marine, novel tools for model-data fusion.
- **TRL 6:** Coastal observation potential demonstrated in relevant coastal systems, hydrological model potential demonstrated in relevant coastal-ocean modelling systems with software code released, dedicated demonstration cases highlighting societal relevance of improved coastal ocean forecasting systems, demonstrated value added by FOCCUS based on all project applications co-designed with MSs, and strategy for the uptake of FOCCUS in CMEMS and MS systems implemented. Links could potentially be made by uptake of FOCCUS deliveries and best practice by existing “disconnected” systems. Connecting the FOCCUS network with services or systems developed or supported by the successive calls for tenders from the National Collaboration Program fostered by CMEMS. Additionally, the output from the co-designed applications could be made available through the Copernicus dedicated Coastal Hub. Synergies and collaboration can take place with outputs from other Horizon Europe projects such as EDITO-Model Lab.

Furthermore, the actions conducted by the project in terms of communication, dissemination, and exploitation enhanced the project's impact while contributing to user engagement ahead of project events planned for 2025. FOCCUS has been steadily building its outreach and engagement across multiple platforms, ensuring visibility among key stakeholders and making sure that the project is on track to achieve its KPIs. As of now, the project has 266 followers on LinkedIn, reflecting growing interest from the marine and coastal data community. The FOCCUS newsletter has attracted 106 subscribers, providing regular updates on project developments. On Twitter (X), the project has 40 followers (having lost 37 followers due to external factors). Meanwhile, FOCCUS video content has garnered 296 views on YouTube, helping to communicate its objectives to a broader audience. These numbers highlight the project's early actions in reaching and engaging with the wider community. Stakeholder's engagement as well as user engagement was targeted for WP8 output, identifying compatible stakeholders and users, and later organising bilateral meetings. The definition of the Coastal Systems Inventory was a success, identifying connections with the various other WPs. MS are keen to have access to it and it will be a very useful tool and easy interface to share this information in various forums like the Copernicus Marine Forum.

Communication and dissemination activities developed during 2024 are further described in section 2.2.10 (WP10).

FOCCUS has begun its dissemination efforts through presentations at conferences and workshops in 2024 (see section 2.2.10) and abstracts were submitted for conferences in 2025, including at EGU General Assembly (April 2025, Vienna, AT), United Nations Ocean Conference (June 2025, Nice, FR) (non-exhaustive list). These engagements focus on showcasing the project's co-production approach and technical developments in coastal data products, fostering dialogue with the scientific community and potential collaborators.

More complete forecasting and analysis is increasingly demanded by coastal users to solve a variety of problems (conflicting tourism and port operation, water quality for aquaculture and bathing, etc.). Achieving more fit-for-use solutions in this area would be of direct benefit for the coastal economy, including a reduction of uncertainty resulting in more efficient, cost-effective operations. In turn, the

project will add value since it will enhance the coastal value of CMEMS products with limited additional investments, making use of existing tools and data. Activities developed towards the uptake of FOCCUS by Member States and Copernicus Marine are also described in section 2.2.10 related to WP10. This includes presentations of FOCCUS during Copernicus Marine Service events to inform the Copernicus Marine Service producers and users communities of the objectives and future outcomes of FOCCUS, presentations of FOCCUS to the Copernicus Marine Forum to inform Member States of on-going developments and engage more Member States than these for which coastal applications are currently being co-developed in FOCCUS. In 2025, activities preparing the uptake of FOCCUS in Copernicus Marine and by Member States will be further developed (WP11), including through the initiation of the Strategic roadmap for the integration in Copernicus Marine (D11.2). The inventory of coastal systems is planned to be presented to the Members of the Copernicus Marine Forum in 2025.

Possibilities for the exploitation/dissemination of FOCCUS outcomes through the Copernicus Coastal Hub ([Coastal Hub | Coastal Hub](#)) will be also analysed. The Copernicus Coastal Hub already provides access to a selection of products of the Copernicus Marine portfolio that are identified as fit-for-purpose for coastal applications. It also showcases many use cases related to coastal problems and policies (see Figure 2.3.2). FOCCUS aims at developing a variety of applications as part of addressing the Environmental and Societal Challenges (WP8, 9, sections 2.2.8, 2.2.9) that are fully aligned with the Copernicus Coastal Hub use case topics. FOCCUS applications will be considered to be described through dedicated use cases in the Copernicus Coastal Hub.

Figure 2.3.2 Use case page of the Copernicus Coastal Hub [The Coastal Hub Use Cases | Coastal Hub](#)

Finally, [FOCCUS has been endorsed](#) in 2024 by the United Nations Decade of the Ocean CoastPredict ([Observing and Predicting the Global Coastal Ocean](#)) Programme. This endorsement will contribute to fostering FOCCUS' legacy, ensuring the lifetime of the project and sustaining its impact beyond the scope of the project's timeline.

In terms of contributions from FOCCUS towards wider impacts, links with the European Digital Twin of

the Ocean (EDITO) have been established and it has been decided in 2024 to organize the General Assemblies of FOCCUS and of EDITO-Model Lab as side-to-side events, in the same place in March 2025, with a common day for the two General Assemblies.

2.4 UPDATE OF THE PLAN FOR EXPLOITATION AND DISSEMINATION OF RESULTS (IF APPLICABLE)

Not applicable.

3. FOLLOW-UP OF RECOMMENDATIONS AND COMMENTS FROM PREVIOUS REVIEW(S) (IF APPLICABLE)

Not applicable.

4. EXPLOITATION PRIMARILY IN NON-ASSOCIATED THIRD COUNTRIES (IF APPLICABLE)

Not applicable.

5. OPEN SCIENCE

FOCCUS implements all mandatory practices of the EU's Open Science policy and contributes to Open Science implementation, aligned with the Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) approach and the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity. FOCCUS implements the approach in all its facets, such as engagement with society, gender, ethics, open data, open science and science education.

Data, models and knowledge will be made available via public-facing, open access (OA) and open source (OS) online platforms e.g., CMEMS and EMODnet that adhere to the Creative Commons BY 4.0 public license for data sharing and uses Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) for machine-machine readability, so that all key actors and stakeholders (from scientists and researchers to policy-makers and the public) have continuous, free and open discovery and access to such data.

All the data produced will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable: see section 1.2.9). For scientific publications, partners of the FOCCUS project will publish in open-access journals, targeting in priority journals with open science policies¹² and will ensure open access of their data and products in all scientific publications with CC BY license or equivalent and through *ad hoc* fees in other journals. Authors will retain sufficient intellectual property rights to comply with OA requirements.

The coordinator Hereon and partners have delivered a Data Management Plan (D1.1 Data Management Plan, first version) establishing guidelines for the management of the data collected during the project. This deliverable describes the type of data FOCCUS collects and how that data will be generated, shared, stored and saved.

FOCCUS will also provide innovative tools, (e.g., for data fusion). These algorithms will be open-source and will be made available on collaborative coding software websites distributed within and outside the project using dedicated open repositories (e.g., GitHub, Gitlab) so that they can be freely available and used by a large community for open science practices. Each algorithm will be associated with a Jupyter notebook that anyone will be able to run. This will ensure an efficient distribution of the algorithms and will deliver a toolbox of algorithms to be used by a large community).

WP10-11 are dedicated to dissemination to promote as early and widely as possible the findings and successful achievements to the scientific community, marine governance stakeholders and the general public. FOCCUS also applies open science by engaging end-users in the design of the applications (WP8-9) and end-users (WP10-11), tailoring applications corresponding to societal needs.

6. DEVIATIONS FROM ANNEX 1 AND ANNEX 2 (IF APPLICABLE)

6.1 TASKS/OBJECTIVES

WP8:

Milestone MS8.1 - Applications definitions workshop, was granted an extension of the delivery date from M13 (January 2024) to M15 (March 2025). This extension was requested in order to:

- Align this workshop with another planned virtual project consortium meeting in early February, to take advantage of this event as a hosting opportunity for the workshop, facilitating cross-WP attendance and collaboration as the virtual consortium meeting aims to include those involved in the entire project.
- Allow for a more robust discussion about the application definitions, due to the likely higher attendance of the virtual consortium meeting in February by multiple partners who represent all of the WPs in the project.
- Gather a detailed summary of workshop results from this wider audience which could be discussed further during the upcoming project GA meeting, ensuring a more productive meeting overall and therefore ensuring that our resulting applications are state-of-the-art and that cross-WP goals are aligned.

WP10:

Deliverable D10.3 - Inventory of EU coastal operational systems, was granted an extension of the delivery date from M12 (December 2024) to M18 (June 2025). This extension was requested in order to:

- To maximise the DCC synergy- DCC targeted the OceanPredict (OP'24) event (18-22 Nov., Paris) as a milestone.
- To lower the burden on contributors and enhance chances of collecting input, we have relied on the DCC inventory for general information, and have proposed a specific complementary survey. This strategy resulted in additional logistic constraints. In particular, the DCC survey platform suffered some delay and as it then targeted the OP'24 event as a milestone for promoting contributions to the DCC survey.
- Extend the timeframe over which our survey is open to contribution. The end of the year is generally very busy, and we believed that having the survey open for at least two months would allow us to identify missing contributions and issue successive contribution requests.
- Present preliminary results in specific forums (e.g., internal meetings in various networks) while providing an explicit list of contributors. Experience gained during our previous EuroGOOS CWG inventory indicated that doing so may trigger more contributions.
- Improve our analysis, by allowing for iteration in the discussion of the results, and eventually complete them with interviews where relevant.

6.2 USE OF RESOURCES

6.2.1 UNFORESEEN SUBCONTRACTING (IF APPLICABLE)

Not applicable.

6.2.2 UNFORESEEN USE OF IN-KIND CONTRIBUTIONS

Not applicable.

HISTORY OF CHANGES		
VERSION	PUBLICATION DATE	CHANGE
1.0	07.01.2025	Initial version.
1.1	15.01.2025	Version 1.1 ready for revision
1.2	25.01.2025	Revisions available, Input provided following the comments
1.3	31.01.2025	Final version ready